

A Comparative Analysis of Prime-Time News Coverage on Public and Private Channels During the 2022 Flash Floods in Balochistan

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Abstract

Balochistan is highly vulnerable to natural disasters due to its distinctive geographical features and socio-economic challenges. It was severely affected by the 2022 floods. This study conducts a comparative analysis of the portrayal of the 2022 flash floods in Balochistan, focusing on the prime-time news coverage provided by two major Pakistani television channels: the state-owned PTV News and the privately-owned Geo News. A mixed-method approach was employed, integrating both qualitative and quantitative content analysis of prime-time news bulletins broadcasted between June to September 2022. The study examines the frequency, duration, and thematic focus of flood-related news, the sources referenced, and the narrative frameworks utilized by the two channels. To support the data analysis, this study utilized the theoretical frameworks of Agenda setting and framing. Agenda setting was employed to assess the allocation of time and space dedicated to the news coverage, while framing was applied to examine the imagery, tone, and other elements shaping the thematic presentation within the news content. The findings indicate notable differences in coverage priorities and framing between PTV News and Geo News. PTV News primarily highlighted government-led relief operations and development initiatives, frequently showcasing official sources and institutional activities. In contrast, Geo News offered a broader spectrum of perspectives, emphasizing the severity of the disaster, the ensuing post-disaster crisis, and the voices of affected citizens, while critically addressing the shortcomings in the government's response.

Keywords: Balochistan, 2022 Flash Floods, News Coverage, Comparative Analysis, Framing

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